

USE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. The article examines the main goal of modern education - preparing an individual capable of social adaptation, self-development, and professional activity. It analyzes the features and significance of interactive teaching methods, which involve active interaction among participants in the educational process. Special attention is given to the explanatory-illustrative technology, its stages, advantages, and disadvantages. The necessity of combining traditional and innovative approaches in teaching is emphasized.

Keywords: modern education, interactive methods, pedagogical technologies, explanatory-illustrative learning, educational work, remedial activities, information and communication competence, educational process.

Interactive methods represent enhanced pedagogical interaction and mutual influence among participants in the educational process through the lens of their individual personalities and personal life experiences. This is a process of intensive intersubjective communication between teacher and student (where the teacher, as the subject of their professional activity, positions the student as the subject of their educational activity). Interactive pedagogical interaction aims to change and improve the behavioral and activity models of participants in the educational process. It is characterized by a high degree of communication intensity among participants, their interactions, exchange of activities, and the variation and diversity of activity types, forms, and methods. It also involves purposeful reflection by participants on their activities and the interaction that has taken place.

In the context of modern society, a teacher's information and communication competence - their ability to solve professional pedagogical tasks using information and communication technologies - is becoming a crucial component of their professionalism.

Interactive learning is a special form of organizing the educational process. Its essence lies in the collaborative activity of students as they master educational material to solve problems that are common yet significant to each individual. This process involves the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and methods of activity.

Today, every educator seeks the most effective ways to improve the educational process. In this regard, teachers' desire to enhance the quality of education is becoming increasingly insistent, with calls to transition from individual methodologies to pedagogical technologies. Compared to teaching based on methodology, educational technology has significant advantages.

Technology is based on a clear definition of the ultimate goal. In traditional pedagogy, the issue of goals is not primary, and the degree of achievement is determined imprecisely, "by eye." In technology, the goal is considered a central component, which allows for a more accurate determination of its achievement.

A technology in which the goal (final and intermediate) is defined very precisely (diagnostically) allows for the development of objective methods to control its achievement. Technology allows minimizing situations where the teacher is faced with a choice and forced to resort to pedagogical improvisations in search of an acceptable option.

Let's highlight the most common groups of pedagogical technologies:

Explanatory-illustrative learning technologies.

Learner-centered teaching technologies.

Developmental learning technologies.

Most often, explanatory and illustrative technologies are criticized, as they are considered traditional and therefore outdated. They are supposedly hindering the reform of the education system by adapting ineffective means to effectively solve problems. Is this really the case?

Analysis of the psychological tools used in explanatory and illustrative technologies, the methods of organizing children's activities, communication, and relationships was conducted only in general education schools. Therefore, one cannot draw one-sided conclusions about the ineffectiveness of explanatory and illustrative technologies in general. D.I. Mendeleev also warned: "Knowledge without upbringing is a sword in the hands of a madman."

The explanatory-illustrative or informative-receptive method involves the teacher presenting information about the object of study through various means, while students perceive, comprehend, and memorize it using all their senses. Informative learning is characterized by the teacher presenting knowledge in a processed, "ready-made" form, which children then perceive and reproduce.

The technology of explanatory-illustrative learning allows for considering students' individual characteristics and improving teacher-student interaction methods. Informative (explanatory-illustrative) teaching is characterized by the teacher presenting knowledge in a processed, "ready-made" form, which students then perceive and reproduce.

The stages of teacher and student activity in this didactic process are as follows: the teacher introduces new knowledge and explains it; facilitates the comprehension of educational information; organizes the generalization and consolidation of knowledge; arranges the application of knowledge and assesses the degree of its assimilation. The student perceives information; comprehends and deepens understanding of the material; summarizes the assimilated material; reinforces the learned content through repetition; and applies the learned material in exercises and assignments.

The stages of the educator's and learner's activities in this didactic process are as follows: the educator introduces new knowledge and explains it; facilitates the comprehension of educational information; organizes the generalization and consolidation of knowledge; arranges the application of knowledge and assesses the degree of its assimilation. The learner perceives information; comprehends and deepens understanding of the material; summarizes the assimilated material; reinforces the learned content through repetition; and applies the learned material in exercises and assignments.

Advantages of communicative learning: systematic approach and relatively low time investment.

Disadvantages: weak implementation of the developmental function of learning, and the student's activity is mainly reproductive. Nevertheless, this is how learning occurs in most cases.

The teacher's task is to address these shortcomings in the process of organizing educational work, which allows for demonstrating the possibilities of explanatory-illustrative technology. A mandatory aspect of the educator's work is conducting educational sessions and classes, during which the teacher addresses not only specific didactic tasks but also corrective ones. Without considering these corrective tasks, it is impossible to discuss the social adaptation of students and the development of their adaptive qualities. Here, one can note the strengths of explanatory-illustrative technology when used in school lessons.

Strengths: organizational clarity of the pedagogical process, systematic nature of teaching, ideological and emotional impact of the educator's personality on the students, versatility and abundance of information, extensive use of visual aids and technical teaching tools.

The purpose of correctional classes is to improve the overall development of students, fill gaps in previous development and learning, provide individual work on insufficiently mastered skills, correct deviations in cognitive and speech development, and prepare students for the perception of new material.

Correctional work is carried out within a holistic approach to student education and development.

1. Informative level: This level clarifies children's understanding and reinforces generally accepted knowledge on the topic, aimed at developing cognitive processes such as memory, attention, and thinking.

2. Personal level: At this level, the child should develop a positive emotional attitude towards the lesson topic. It is necessary to ensure that they want to apply the acquired knowledge to themselves. Here, approval, support, and acceptance of the child as they are are necessary.

3. Awareness level: At this level, the child learns to understand what is happening to them, why they act in certain ways, why feelings arise, and what thoughts exist. This level develops the ability for self-regulation, self-knowledge, self-understanding, and self-control. It also fosters understanding of what other people think, feel, and do. All three levels of teaching and upbringing must be present in the lesson and create an enriched developmental environment for the participants.

Expected results:

1. Students know and understand the content of the conducted lessons.

2. The psychotherapeutic effect will be evident in the student's trust in the teacher, their desire to connect with them, and their openness and interest in the lessons. It will also result in reduced emotional tension, increased psychological comfort, and positive feelings.

3. Although explanatory-illustrative methods are not inherently developmental, they manifest in children's interest and desire to expand their knowledge, apply this knowledge in practice, and use the acquired skills in other types of activities.

Explanatory-illustrative technology will have a developmental nature of learning if it is used alongside other technologies (problem-solving, game-based, and collaborative technologies).

The relevance of the above is determined not only by social demand, but also by an individual's need for self-determination and self-expression in the context of modern information society.

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